

Power Consumption for Processing some Wood Species in Nigerian Sawmills

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Processing woods requires power which is scarcely available in Nigeria due to lack of proper planning and poor power generation infrastructure. This study seeks to establish the different power requirement for processing commonly available species of wood in Nigeria. Twenty-four (24) sawmills across five south western states were selected for the study. Measuring instruments namely: wattmeter; stop watch and measuring tape were used to measure the current, voltage and power factor; time of operation and sizes of timber log during operation respectively in each of the sawmills. The results show that the power consumed by the different wood species varies, with *Iroko (Milicia excelsa)* consuming the highest power and *Igba (Parkia biglobosa)* consumes the least. The data, such as the ones provided in the study will enable the authority to project the quantity of energy needed by the sectors to enable proper planning and implementations.

Keywords: power; energy; wood; sawmill; Nigeria

1.0 Introduction

Sawmills are facilities equipped with machines such as band saw, re-sawing; and where logs from the forest are cut into lumber [1]. Majority of the saw mill industries are located in the wood producing rain forest areas of the Country in which the Western States are among. The largest concentration of sawmills is in Lagos, Ekiti, Osun, Cross River, Ondo, Oyo, Imo, Edo, Delta and Ogun States. Together, they accounted for over 90 % of the saw milling activities in the Country [2]. This indicated that guaranteed log supply is a major factor in the location of sawmills in the Country.

From available evidence, the number of wood based industries in Nigeria has been increasing except for sawmills, which declined from 1700 in 1993 to 1349 in 1997. As at 1993, the General Wood and Veneer Consultant Ltd, Canada who was employed by the Federal Department of Forestry to carry out studies on the wood based industries revealed that there were altogether 1715 wood industries in Nigeria consisting of 1700 sawmills, 8 plywood mills, 4 particle board mills and 3 paper mills. However, by 1997, the Beak Constants Ltd in collaboration with Geomatics international Canada who was employed by the Federal Department of Forestry to carry out a Forest Resource Study revealed that the number of wood based industry had declined from the level of 1715 in 1993 to 1373. These consist of 1349 sawmills, 10 Plywood mills, 4 Particleboard mills, 3 Paper mills and 7 Match and splints factories. The major wood processing industries in Nigeria are typically large

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capacity facilities such as large sawmills, plywood mill, pulp and paper plants etc. In particular, sawmills are designed to handle large diameter logs. Sawmills are essentially distributed between small, medium and large scale in the proportion of 81%: 13%: 6%. Although the number of sawmills decreased, production has not decreased commensurately. This is because, though wood industries are finding it increasingly difficult to obtain desirable sizes of popular tree species like *Mansonialtissima*, *Miliciaexclesa* and *Khaya* species from Nigerian forests, they have been forced to expand the range of exploited species to species which hitherto were regarded as uneconomic.

As revealed by the study carried out by Segun and Yahaya [3], as at 1990, the Nigerian sawmill capacity was estimated at 11,684,000m³/year in log equivalent and capacity utilisation was 46% i.e. 5,422,000m³/year. It was estimated that by 1993 estimated capacity had dropped to 5,842,000m³ while production was 2,711,000m³. However, based on the findings of Beak International and the field survey carried out by them, it was estimated that by 1997, the capacity would have dropped to 4,635,800 with a corresponding output of about 2,000,000m³. Production also might have gradually declined.

According to Ogunwusi [4], the installed capacity in the sawmill industry in Nigeria rose from 8,831,750m³ in 1988 to 15,793,188m³ in 1992. It then decreased to 10,900,000 in 1996 and subsequently increased to 14,684,000m³ in 2002 and 11,734,000m³ in 2010. Capacity utilization within these periods was 6,994,660m³, 6,031,922m³, 7,069,145, and 3,800,000m³ respectively. This represented 79%, 38%, 39%, 35% and 32% capacity utilization respectively. Total number of sawmills decreased from 1617 in 1990 to 910 in 1992. It rose to 1252 in 1996 and to 1259 in year 2002. In 2010, the number of sawmills in Nigeria stabilized at 1325.

Ohagwu and Ugwuishiwu [5] revealed that there are different kinds of wood available in Nigeria, irrespective of their location and usage. They include: *Apa*, *Black Afara*, *White Afara*, *Afromosia*, *Gmelina*, *Idigbo*, *Canarium*, *Okan*, *Antiaria*, *Lagos Mahogany*, *Berlinia*, *Ekki*, *Scented Guarea*, *Dry zone Mahogany*, *Camwood*, *Pterygote*, *Albizia*, *Alstonia*, *Makore*, *White sterculia*, *Owewe*, *Dist*, *Okwen*, *Obeche*, *Opepe*, *African Walnut*, *Mansonia*, *Teak*, *Ebony*, *Guarea*, *Iroko*, *Abura*, *Ogea*, *Pterocarpus*, *Erimado*, *Agba*, *Akpu*, *Danta*, *Celtis*, *walnut*, etc. Meanwhile, processing these woods require different amount of power, which for proper planning, needs to be established. This study seeks to establish the different power requirement for processing the commonly available species of wood in Nigeria.

2.0. Methodolgy

Twenty four sawmills were selected across five States; Oyo (four), Osun (five), Ogun (eighth), Ondo (five) and Lagos (two). Measuring instruments namely: wattmeter; stop watch and measuring tape were used to measure the current, voltage and power factor; time of operation and sizes of timber log during operation respectively in each of the sawmills.

The energy measured includes manual (i.e. human) and electrical energy involved in the conversion of a timber log to planks of 1inch by 12inches (0.025m by 0.305m).

2.1. Manual energy

According to Odigboh [6], at the maximum continuous energy consumption rate of 0.30kW and conversion efficiency of 25%, the physical power output of a normal human labourer in tropical climates is approximately 0.075kW sustained for an 8–10 h workday.

Mathematically:

$$E_m = 0.075Nt \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

where:

- E_m is the manual energy in kWh,
- 0.075 is the average power of a normal human labour in kW,
- N is the number of persons involved in an operation and
- t is the useful time spent to accomplish a given task in hours.

The number of people working in each sawmill per operation was counted and recorded.

All the mills selected were visited and evaluated over the same period and season, and as a result, the error of seasonal changes was eliminated.

2.2. Data collection

The primary energy resources that were used in these analyses are energy gotten from the two main sources, that is; electricity from the national grid and electricity from fossil fuel. The power rating of the electrical devices and capacity of each unit were collected from the site’s manager or the personnel in charge. The production processes were monitored and data collected for weeks depending on the size of the site being considered. The time it took to complete each process was also recorded. The energy analysis are based on process analysis in which every successive production step were estimated and the material input to each operation also were indicated [7]. The principal operations involved in sawmilling in the South Western Nigeria are indicated in Figure 1

Fig. 1: Processing steps for log in sawmills in South Western Nigeria.

2.3 Evaluation of electrical energy

The electrical energy used by the log processing machines is predicted by using a formula developed by Rajput [8]. The electrical energy usage by equipment was obtained as the product of the rated power of each motor of the plant or equipment and the number of hours of operation. A motor efficiency of 80% was assumed to compute the electrical inputs [8]. Mathematically, the formula is given as:

$$E_p = \eta Pt \text{ ----- (2)}$$

where, E_p is the electrical energy consumed in kWh, P is the rated power of the motor in kW, t is the hours of operation in hours and η is efficiency of the motor or power factor usually taken as 80% or 0.8.

3.0. Results

A minimum of five sawmill spanned across the three senatorial districts in each of *Osun*, *Ondo*, *Oyo* and *Ogun* States and two in Lagos states were visited. These sawmills are; (1) *Bisi abass* sawmill (*Osun East-Ife central*), (2) *Adegoke* sawmill (*Osun Central-Ikirun*), (3) *Olorunda* sawmill (*Osun Central-Osogbo*), (4) *Alhaji Kabiru* sawmill (*Osun West-Ede*), (5) *Ojebola* sawmill (*Osun West-Ejigbo*), (6) *St Luke* sawmill (*Ondo south-Okeigbo*), (7) *Sesan* sawmill (*Ondo south-Okitipupa*), (8) *Alawiye* sawmill (*Ondo Central-Akure south*), (9) *Oluwabamise* sawmill (*Ondo North-Ikare*), (10) *Olukayode* sawmill (*Ondo North-Akungba*), (11) *Ranmilowo Oluwa Osiele* (*Ogun central*), (12) *Olorunwa Lafenwa* (*Ogun central*), (13) *Alhaji Isiaka Olaoluwa Aiyetoro* (*Ogun west*), (14) *Ogo Oluwa Ipokia* (*Ogun west*), (15) *Iyanu Oluwa Ijebu igbo* (*ogun east*), (16) *Oremeji Ogere Remo* (*Ogun east*), (17) *EDMED Abiodun Atiba road* (*Oyo central*), (18) *Iyanu Oluwa Sabo* (*Oyo central*), (19) *Al- Wajud Ido* (*Oyo south*), (20) *Owonikoko Igbo ora* (*Oyo south*), (21) *Oke Baba, Ebute Meta*, Lagos, (22) *Okegbegun, Ikorodu*, (23) *Pakoto, Ifo* (*Ogun state*), (24) *Gawan* sawmill, Camp, *Abeokuta* (*Ogun state*). Twelve (12) sawmills were using diesel generator as at the time the measurements were taken, this enables the data collection and analysis on the alternative energy source to be easily carried out. Tables 1 and 2 show both derived parameters and direct measurements taken during the operation in each sawmill indicated against the respective wood species. The parameters are log length, log volume, time taken for processing each log, electrical power, power factor, electrical energy and manual energy.

Table 1: Table showing parameters from visited sawmills in Osun and Ondo states

	Wood Species	Average log length (m)	Volume of log (m ³)	Operation time (hr)	Electrical Power (kW)	Electrical Energy (kWh)	Manual Energy (kWh)
1	<i>Afara (Terminalia Superba)</i>	3.32	2.58	0.24	17.65	4.24	0.07
2	<i>Opepe (Naulea Diderrichii)</i>	3.11	2.14	0.36	6.28	2.26	0.11
3	<i>Afara (Terminalia Superba)</i>	3.41	3.81	0.28	19.15	5.36	0.08
4	<i>Afara (Terminalia Superba)</i>	3.06	2.15	0.29	16.96	4.92	0.09
5	<i>Iroko (Milicia excelsa)</i>	2.99	2.99	0.38	47.15	17.92	0.11
6	<i>Omo (Cordia Millenii)</i>	3.61	2.22	0.22	7.61	1.67	0.07
7	<i>Obeche (Triplochyton Scleroxylon)</i>	3.83	2.18	0.22	5.78	1.27	0.07
8	<i>Mahogany (Khaya Ivorensis)</i>	3.49	2.48	0.29	12.09	3.51	0.09
9	<i>Mahogany (Khaya Ivorensis)</i>	3.51	2.58	0.31	13.1	4.06	0.09
10	<i>Iroko (Milicia excelsa)</i>	2.72	4.54	0.36	52.36	18.85	0.11

Table 2: Table showing parameters from visited sawmills in Oyo and Ogun states

	Wood Species	Average log length (m)	Volume of log (m ³)	Operation time (hr)	Electrical Power (kW)	Electrical Energy (kWh)	Manual Energy (kWh)
11	<i>Igba (Parkia biglobosa)</i>	3.30	4.44	0.24	17.65	4.24	0.11
12	<i>Afara (Terminalia Superba)</i>	3.50	2.68	0.36	39.62	14.26	0.13
13	<i>Igba (Parkia biglobosa)</i>	3.27	4.22	0.28	14.64	4.10	0.11
14	<i>Igba (Parkia biglobosa)</i>	3.45	4.81	0.29	16.96	4.92	0.19
15	<i>Iroko (Milicia excelsa)</i>	2.85	4.58	0.38	47.15	17.92	0.31
16	<i>Opepe (Naulea Diderrichii)</i>	3.27	3.79	0.32	13.88	4.44	0.37
17	<i>Igba (Parkia biglobosa)</i>	3.66	4.97	0.22	5.78	1.27	0.12
18	<i>Opepe (Naulea Diderrichii)</i>	3.43	2.66	0.29	12.09	3.51	0.28
19	<i>Afara (Terminalia Superba)</i>	3.32	3.16	0.31	13.1	4.06	0.09
20	<i>Iroko (Milicia excelsa)</i>	2.43	4.86	0.36	52.36	18.85	0.24

4.0 Discussion

Falemara et al. [9], in their article (physical properties of selected indigenous wood species) carried out a research to determine the physical properties of the selected woods. It should be known that the hardness of woods will affect the amount of power consumption. So it means that the harder the wood, the more energy that will be required to process it. From the results shown in Tables 1 and 2, it is clear that the differences in hardness of the log of wood have led to the differences in power consumption for each wood species. The work of [9] revealed the density of the wood species such as *Terminalia Superba (Afara)* is 555.08 kg/m³, *Naulea Diderrichii (Opepe)* is 739.45 kg/m³, *Milicia Excelsa (Iroko)* is 653.66 kg/m³, *Cordia millenii (Omo)* is 436.51 kg/m³, *Triplochiton Scleroxylon (Obeche)* is 407.50 kg/m³, *Khaya Ivorensis (Mahogany)* is 468 kg/m³. They further classified the densities of woods as high, medium and low density. *Opepe* falls in the category of high density and thus means it is the hardest among woods considered; *Iroko*, *Afara*, and Mahogany falls in the category of medium density and thus they can also be classified among the hard woods; while *Omo* and *Obeche* falls in the category of low density and thus means soft woods.

5.0 Conclusion

Energy challenges in Nigeria can be attributed partly to shortage of power generation infrastructure and lack of proper planning. If there are data that will enable the authority to project the quantity of energy needed by different sectors, then it will be easier to make necessary and adequate planning to put in place the required infrastructure for the generation. Sawmill industry; being one important sector of the economy that depends heavily on energy will be properly accounted for with respect to energy requirement by the use of data presented in this work.

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